

The causal relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth across states in the U.S.

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Abstract—This paper examines the causal relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth across fifty states in the United States. Only one study has investigated the relationship under the same study scope in the literature. Using panel data of fifty states over the period from 1990 to 2017, the result shows that in the long run, a 1% increase in per capita electricity consumption (EC) significantly increases per capita gross domestic product (GDP) by 0.85% (1.19%, 2.57%) by applying panel dynamic least squares (DOLS), panel fully modified least squares method (FMOLS), and panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model respectively. The positive impact of electricity consumption on economic growth also holds in the short run. However, this relationship is both positive and negative for specific state estimation. The causality test result also shows a uni-directional causality that runs from electricity consumption to economic growth.

Index Terms—Electricity consumption, Economic growth, energy consumption, renewable energy

1 INTRODUCTION

The United States is the second biggest electricity consuming country in the world. Electricity consumption in the U.S. increased dramatically for the past decade, with 5% yearly average growth. Since electricity is an essential input to produce a majority of goods and services, any change in electricity consumption is expected to have an impact on economic growth ([EIA]). In addition, the U.S. is one the leading countries in consuming renewable energy. In the past 10 years, renewable energy consumption has increased 100% and it is considered as the fastest-growing energy source in the U.S. ([C2SE]). Since renewable energy accounts for 17% of electricity generation, it is important to control for this variable while analyzing the causal impact of electricity consumption on economic growth.

Even though there are numerous studies have investigated the relationship between

electricity consumption and economic growth, there is only one study that investigated the causal impact of the two variables at the state level. In order to address the scarcity of literature studying the causality between electricity consumption and economic growth, and to improve the limitations of the previous study, this paper examines the causal relationship across fifty states in the U.S. by controlling for renewable energy consumption, capital stock and labor force participation.

An increase in electricity consumption likely increases state gross domestic product due to increasing the number of goods and services produced. Furthermore, electricity industry creates an active job market by offering higher wage, which results in reducing unemployment and improving job quality. Additionally, electricity industry brings more investment opportunities to the country, and since investment is one of four key factors of GDP, an increases in investment positively affects economic growth. Conversely, since there is an investment attraction to electricity industry, it possibly takes away the investment from other energy factors

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that contributes more in economic growth. As a result, an increase in electricity investment may reduce economic growth. Overall, it remains an empirical question as to the net causal effect of electricity consumption on economic growth.

In my analysis, I use panel data of fifty states over the period from 1990 to 2017. The per capita state gross domestic product is collected from Bureau of Economic Analysis at chained 2012 dollars. The electricity consumption and renewable energy consumption are collected from U.S Energy Information Administration. The labor force participation and state population are collected from Federal Reserve Economic Data. Additionally, instead of using a proxy variable for capital stock, I use the newly available capital stock data for all the states, which is a major improvement in my research. I begin with a general per capita measure of electricity consumption, renewable energy consumption and capital stock by dividing these variables by total state population. I then proceed to test for the cross sectional dependence among states in order to utilize heterogenous panel technique. In order to estimate the long-run relationship among variables, I estimate the long-run elasticities of per capita gross domestic with respect to electricity consumption, renewable energy, capital stock and labor force participation using panel dynamic least squares (DOLS), panel fully modified least squares method (FMOLS), and panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. The panel causality is also conducted to report the causal relationship among variables.

Our result shows that there is enough evidence suggesting the presence of cross sectional dependence in the estimated equation and all the variables but Ln_EC are non-stationary at level ($I(0)$). The long-run estimation reports that a 1% increase in per capita electricity consumption leads to a 0.85% (1.19%, 2.57%) increase in per capita gross domestic product by applying panel dynamic least squares (DOLS), panel fully modified least squares method (FMOLS), and panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model respectively. Regarding to other variables, an increase in renewable energy and labor force participation reduce eco-

nomical growth. Additionally, an increase in capital stock increases gross domestic product by about 1%. The panel causality test also suggests a uni-directional causality that runs from electricity consumption to gross domestic product. Furthermore, the long-run estimation result varies among state specific estimation.

The primary contribution of the study is emphasizing the importance of focusing on the causal relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth at the state level since the U.S. is a big country with different economic and political system across states. My second contribution is addressing the missing variable problem of the previous study by controlling for renewable energy in the model, which results in avoiding biased estimation.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Even though several studies have examined the relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth with some studies reporting a positive relationship (eg: Narayan and Smyth [2009], Bayar et al. [2014], Yoo and Kwak [2010]) and other studies reporting negative relationship (Carfora et al. [2019]), there is a limited number of studies on the causal impact of electricity consumption on economic growth (eg: Narayan and Smyth [2009]). To investigate the causal impact, in this section I present studies based on the level of geographical aggregation: cross-countries studies, single-country study and state-level studies.

Numerous studies have explored the causal relationship between economic growth and electricity consumption at cross-country study in order to investigate whether the same policy target equally strikes all the countries in the same region or organization (Al-Iriani [2006], Bohm [2008], Ciarreta and Zarraga [2010], Chen et al. [2007], Hossain and Saeki [2011], Lee and Chang [2007]); and the efficiency of policy implication on energy conservation in some parts which are less paid attention on of the world (Narayan and Smyth [2009], Osman et al. [2016]). By applying Granger causality test, which helps to measure the ability to predict economic growth by using the prior data

of electricity consumption or the reserve prediction, several studies have investigated the causal impact of electricity consumption on economic growth (Chen et al. [2007], Bohm [2008]). For example, Chen et al. [2007] investigates the relationship in ten industrializing countries and the findings suggest that in the short run, economic growth Granger causes electricity consumption but not vice versa; and in the long run, there exists a bi-directional relationship between economic growth and electricity consumption. Bohm [2008] supports Chen et al. [2007]'s conclusion by examining the impact in European union. In addition, several studies apply vector of autoregression (VAR) to estimate the impact and conclude that economic growth positively causes electricity consumption (Lee and Chang [2007], Al-Iriani [2006]). Another study applies vector error correlation model (VECM) to estimate the causal relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth and suggests that there is a negative causal impact of electricity consumption on economic growth (Ciarreta and Zarraga [2010]). Prior research substantiates the belief that there is an evidence of a causal impact between economic growth and electricity consumption in the long run at multi-country level (e.g: Hossain and Saeki [2011], Narayan and Smyth [2009], Osman et al. [2016]). A potential limitation of cross-country analysis is that the result may not comparable for all countries if they have differences in electricity consumption or economic growth. For example, in the research of Chen et al. [2007], Philippine's electricity consumption per capita was 696 while Canada's was 15,588 (World Bank [a]). Since Canada's electricity consumption is about 22 times of Philippine's, the impact of electricity consumption on economic growth between these two countries is possibly different.

Many studies have examined the causal relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth at country level in order to obtain policy implications and recommend better policies for a specific country in both short run and long run (Abosedra et al. [2009], Altinay and Karagol [2005], Bao and Liu [2019], Ghosh [2002], Shahbaz et al. [2011], Shiu

and Lam [2004], Yoo [2005]). Investigating the impact at the country level is crucial because it presented a major shift from prior research moving the focus back to a specific country away from cross-country level. This major shift corrects the limitation of cross-country analysis, that is, it helps to provide a reliable information of the causal impact between electricity consumption and economic growth for one specific country. For example, since there is a wide gap in GDP per capita between Canada and Philippines, the appliance standard efficiency policy in Canada will not be applicable in Philippines due to the high cost of efficient appliances. On one hand, applying error correlation model (ECM) method, several studies conclude that electricity consumption causes real GDP, but no evidence of reversal causality (Abosedra et al. [2009], Altinay and Karagol [2005], Shiu and Lam [2004]) while other studies find a positive bi-directional causality exists for economic growth and electricity consumption (Yoo [2005]). On the other hand, since an increase in income will encourage people to switch to a better and higher quality fuels such as electricity, the causality may run from economic growth to electricity consumption. At a country level, several studies find a positive unidirectional causality running from economic growth to electricity consumption, that is, an increase in GDP leads to a growth in electricity consumption (Ghosh [2002], Shahbaz et al. [2011]). The single-country level focus, however, may fail to take a country with a large area such as China or Russia into account. This is because within a large country, electricity consumption, economic condition, weather and number of populations may largely differ across province or state. For example, in Guangdong province in China, the electricity consumption is 872 billion kWh while it is only 24 billion kWh in Hainan province (Bao and Liu [2019]). Due to this significant difference, the relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth in these two cities possibly are not unique. Since the conclusion is drawn for the whole country in general, it may create a problem for understanding the impact of electricity consumption in economic growth for a specific

provinces or states; and also, the implication of country policy may not be effective across places within the country.

To the best of my knowledge, only one study has investigated the causal relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth at a more disaggregated level within a country. Churchill and Ivanovski [2020] focus on states and territories across Australia and argue that every state and territory has a different economic condition. Some states and territories such as Victoria are more about "service-based" development, which refers to the principle economic activity is the services supply rather than manufacturing (Churchill and Ivanovski [2020]). These service-based states and territories likely consume less electricity compared to the resources-based states and territories such as Western Australia. In addition, each state has its own policy such as feed-in tariffs and auctions to enhance electricity saving (OECD. [2019]). The difference in policies differently affects electricity consumption across states and territories. For example, Victoria state develops Victorian Environment and Resource Efficiency Plans, which encourages to reduce the electricity consumption, may impact economic growth in the state. In order to better address heterogeneity problem, which refers to the differences across the units being examined, Churchill and Ivanovski [2020] examine the panel data based on tests relating to cross-sectional dependence. This method helps to ensure the reliability by taking the advantages of inter-state levels while estimating the relationship between economic growth and electricity consumption in the long run. The panel result shows that in the long run, if electricity consumption per capita increases by 1%, per capita gross state output will increase by 0.314%. There is also a positive relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth in the short run. However, the effect of electricity consumption on economic growth is not consistent based on each state's long-run and short-run estimation. Since the renewable energy provides an important evidence of the energy development, the study might have benefited from controlling for the interrelationship between renewable energy

and electricity consumption.

Although there has not been any studies considering renewable energy in examining the causal relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth at the state level, it is reasonable to control for the role of renewable energy while estimating the causal relationship. This is because renewable energy directly affects electricity consumption which indirectly results in influencing economic growth. Recently, there has been a large volume of literature on the relationship between renewable energy and economic growth. While many studies show that there is a nonlinear positive relationship between renewable energy and economic growth (eg: Al-mulali et al. [2014], Alper and Oguz [2016], Ibrahim [2015], Ntanos et al. [2018]), there is some evidence that electricity consumption from renewable energy negatively affects economic growth (eg: Halkos and Tzeremes [2014], Ocal and Aslan [2013]) or it has no impact on economic growth (Pao and Fu [2013]).

Even though there have been several studies explore the link between electricity consumption and economic growth in the U.S. (Apergis and Payne [2012], Hirsh and Koomey [2015]), no study has examined this relationship at the state level. Since the U.S. is a large country consisting of fifty states which have their own economic and political system, there is possibly a difference in the effect of electricity consumption on economic growth across these states. Therefore, our first contribution is adding a new study about electricity consumption and economic growth about the U.S. at state-level focus to the literature. Second, since the U.S. is one of the leading countries in renewable energy, which is the fastest growing energy source in the country, and there possibly a link between electricity consumption and renewable energy and they can be complementing in influence economic growth, we address the missing variable limitation of the existing study by including renewable energy in the model. By extending the framework from Churchill and Ivanovski [2020] and correcting for their limitation, the modified model allows us to deal with cross-sectional dependence and heterogeneity

across fifty states in the U.S..

3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In order to understand the relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth, it is essential to understand why electricity consumption could affect economic growth. Electricity consumption could lead to an increase in economic growth because of three possible reasons: electricity is an input in the production, electricity industry brings investment opportunities and electricity industry creates more jobs and improves job quality. Even though electricity is an important input, the influence of electricity consumption on the economy may differ from state to state due to the economic structure of each state.

Electricity is an important input factor in the production of all sectors. For example, in 2018, the industrial sector accounted for 41.86% of total electricity consumptions while the machine drives are the largest use of electricity by U.S. manufacturers, accounted for 48.2 % ([EIA]). An increase in electricity consumption generates more outputs include goods and services. For example, using electricity as an input improves food and seed preservation, which helps to increase the productivity in agriculture sector. In addition, in service sector, electricity enables efficient services by supporting to run machines and operation which maintains a flow of energy in the production process.

Electricity industry brings investment opportunities to the country. Since investment is one of the four key factors of GDP, an increase in investment leads to a growth in economy. Since 2010, there has been a steady increase in investment in electricity transmission in the U.S.. In 2010, the investment amount is \$10.2 billion, and this number increases to \$21.0 billion in 2018 (Group et al. [2011]). Investment in distribution also increases in order to maintain reliability and increase market efficiency([EIA]). An increase in electricity consumption requires new investment in this area, which results in increasing economic growth.

Electricity industry may also reduce unemployment rate and improves job quality. In

particular, the electricity power industry accounts for 5% of total GDP in the U.S. . It also created an active job market for people, which brought more than seven million jobs to the market in 2017. The electricity industry also attracted workers because it pays twice the national medium wage (Association). According to Okun's Law, unemployment rate negatively affects potential GDP. Therefore, a potential improvement in employment rate by opening more jobs and offering higher salary in electricity industry possibly increases economic growth. In addition, since labor is an important input in the electricity industry, an increase in the input factor of electricity production generates more electricity to supply to other industries. As a result, amount of goods and services produced in the market may increase, which positively affects economic growth. However, this impact may differ depends on the employment rate and electricity consumption of each state.

The way electricity consumption affects economic growth may be different in states that use renewable energy because renewable energy increasingly is an important input of the electricity production. Since renewable energy does not require fuel and transportation cost, it is the cheapest source of electricity production (Forsberg [2009]). Using renewable energy decreases the electricity production cost, which reduces the cost of producing goods and services. Moreover, the renewable energy industry has also created a great job market. For example, there was 8.1 million people employed worldwide in the renewable energy industry in 2016. In the U.S., there will be 4 million job created by 2030 if a 30% renewable portfolio standard were to be implemented (Wei et al. [2010]). Therefore, renewable energy and electricity consumption are expected to be complements in influencing the economy growth. However, the impact of the consumption of electricity, which generated by renewable energy, on economic growth may differ from states to states. The impact may be significant in the states that use most renewable energy such as Vermont and may be relatively small in other states such as Delaware or Florida.

There are concerns that these same mechanisms may work in reverse. Even though electricity consumption is an important input in the production of all goods and services, the electricity consumption may not affect all states the same way since states have different industries which may require different amount of electricity usage. Then it is not necessary that increasing electricity consumption will increase economic growth in all states. Some may be unaffected or even see a decrease in their growth. In addition, attracting more investment from electricity industry can take away investments from other energy industries, which contribute more in economic growth. As a result, an increase in electricity investment possibly reduces economic growth. Furthermore, an increase in renewable energy possibly negatively affects economic growth due to its intermittency and storage limitation. Since renewable energy production highly relies on the weather which is unpredictable, and renewable energy storage is expensive and high technology required, it is difficult to make renewable energy available all the time. The consequence could be an interruption in producing electricity, results in reducing the good and services produced in other industries that required electricity as an input factor.

4 METHODOLOGY

The relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth is investigated by taking a double-log of the simple production function which relates inputs such as electricity consumption, renewable energy, labor and capital stock to GDP. The empirical equation is given as:

$$\ln GDP_{it} = \lambda_{1i} \ln EC_{it} + \lambda_{2i} \ln RE_{it} + \lambda_{3i} \ln CS_{it} + \lambda_{4i} \ln LF_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

where per capita real gross state product (GDP_it) for a state i in year t depends on per capita electricity consumption (EC_it), per capita renewable energy consumption (RE_it), state labor force participation rate (LF_it) and per capita real capital stock (CS_it);

and $\lambda_{1i}, \lambda_{2i}, \lambda_{3i}, \lambda_{4i}$ are the elasticities of per capita state output with respect to per capita state electricity consumption, per capita renewable energy consumption, per capita labor force participation rate and per capita capital stock.

The coefficient of interest is λ_{1i} to assess if electricity consumption has an impact on economic growth. If λ_{1i} is significantly greater than zero, an increase in electricity consumption significantly increases state gross domestic product. If λ_{1i} is significantly smaller than zero, a growth of state electricity consumption reduces economic growth. Two concerns, though, the domestic factors such as efficiency energy policy or intra-national trade can have spill overs effects across state which results in arising cross sectional dependence (CSD) problem. If the CSD problem exists and is not dealt appropriately, the interest coefficient λ_{1i} will be biased. The second concern is the heterogeneity which refers to differences across all the states that examined. If there is unobserved heterogeneity which is not accounted by appropriate technique, then the correlation between (EC_it) and error term will be non-zero, (EC_it) therefore will be biased.

In order to identify if there is cross sectional dependence in the panel data, before processing the panel data analysis, I use Pearson CD (2004). The advantage of Pearson CD (2004) model is that it is still valid for heterogeneous model and non-stationary model (De Hoyos and Sarafidis [2006]). Therefore, the result of the Pearson CD (2004) method is still reliable if unobserved heterogeneity exists. Pearson CD (2004) is given as:

$$CD = \sqrt{\frac{2T}{N(N-1)}} \left(\sum_i^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \hat{p}_{ij} \right) \quad (2)$$

The null hypothesis of the test assumes that there is an evidence of cross-sectional dependence $CSD \rightarrow N(0,1)$ for $N \rightarrow \infty$ while the alternative hypothesis assume that there is no evidence of CSD existence (De Hoyos and Sarafidis [2006]).

To address the endogeneity problem, I estimate equation (1) by using panel dynamic

least squares (DOLS)(Stock and Watson 1993) and panel fully modified least squares method (FMOLS) (Phillips and Hasen 1990). These two methods allow heterogeneity across all states examined such as "individual-specific time trends, individual-specific fixed effect and time-specific fixed effects" (Mark and Sul [2003]).

In the equation, I also control for renewable energy consumption. Since the renewable energy is the input of electricity production, controlling for this variable avoids omitting relevant variable problem.

5 DATA

The data come from 1990-2017. This is a panel data for all 50 states over 27 years from 1990 to 2017. The per capita real GDP at chained 2012 dollars data at state level is collected from Bureau of Economic Analysis(World Bank [b]). The advantage of the chain dollar is to allow the comparison of real GDP in different years from 1990 to 2017 because the method adjusts inflation over time. The state labor force participation rate, which is the number of all employed and unemployed workers divided against the state's civilian population, is collected from Federal Reserve Economic Data (FRED) The data of renewable energy consumption and electricity consumption, which is the total consumed of all residential, industrial, commercial and transportation customers, are collected from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA). Another variable that I also need to control for is the real state level capital stock. Since the data is not available at any standard site,it is collected from The Center for Financial Development and Stability (CFDS) at Henan University (Garofalo and Yamarik [2002], El-Shagi and Yamarik [2019]). Compared to other previous studies in which they used proxy variable, the availability of capital stock data is used in my paper can be a potential improvement in giving a better result.

The real gross state product (GDP_{it}) is expressed in millions at chained 2012 dollars while the labor force participation (LF_{it}) is in percentage and is seasonal adjusted and the real capital stock (CS_{it}) is in million of 2009 US

dollars. The renewable energy (RE) is expressed in Trillion BTU and the electricity consumption (EC_{it}) is in Megawatthours. While the per capita real GDP is available, I create the real per capita for renewable energy consumption, electricity consumption and real capital stock but labor force participation by dividing them by the state population. The population data is collected from FRED and it is expressed in term of thousands of people.

6 RESULT

In the following section, I focus on the relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth by undertaking various empirical methods and report the findings. It is also necessary to pay attention to the effect of renewable energy consumption on economic growth. Within each subsection, I discuss the overall result of each empirical method and briefly provide analysis.

6.1 Cross sectional dependent (CSD) test.

The cross sectional independence test is applied to test for the null hypothesis of cross sectional independence. The result is reported at Table 1.

Table 1 shows the results of cross sectional independence test using five different methods. The third column shows the p-value corresponds to each t-value in the second column. Since the p-values of all these methods are about zero, I am confident in rejecting the null hypothesis at one percent significance. Therefore, it is important to account for cross sectional dependence in order to estimate the unobserved factors across states.

6.2 Test for unit root considered cross sectional dependence.

Since cross sectional dependence exists, the Im, Pesaran, and Shin test is applied to test for unit root. The result is reported in Table 2. The result shows that at level, all variables but Ln_EC are non-stationary at 1% significance. Ln_EC is non-stationary at 5% significance. All variables are stationary at their 1st differences, that is, they are integrated at order one (I(1)).

TABLE 1
Cross sectional independence result.

Test	Statistic	Prob
Breusch-Pagan Chi-Square	15187.560	0.000*
Pearson LM Normal	281.076	0.000*
Pearson CD Normal	112.648	0.000*
Friedman Chi-Square	772.673	0.000*
Frees Q	17.188	0.000*
* indicate the rejection of the null hypothesis of cross sectional independence at 1% significance level		
The asymptotic critical values are 0.17, 0.12 and 0.09 at 1%, 5% and 10% significance level respectively		

Therefore, the long-run relationship may exist among these five variables.

TABLE 2
Unit root test result

Variable	Im_Pesaran at level	Im-PE	Im_Pesaran at 1st difference	Im-PE
	W Stat	P-value	W Stat	P-value
Ln_GDP	-0.426	0.335	-23.448	0.000*
Ln_EC	-2.609	0.004**	-27.350	0.000*
Ln_RE	2.738	0.997	-26.180	0.000*
Ln_CS	2.830	0.997	-16.499	0.000*
LF	5.29	1	-15.616	0.000*
* & ** indicate the rejection of the null hypothesis that variable is stationary at 1% and 5% significance level respectively.				

6.3 Panel cointegration test.

Since it is reasonable to believe there is a long-run relationship among Ln_GDP, Ln_EC, Ln_RE, Ln_CS and LF, I continue to test for panel cointegration among variables. The null hypothesis is that there is cointegration among variable and the alternative hypothesis states that there is no cointegration among variables. Table 3 shows the result of the Pedroni Cointegration test for the null hypothesis of no cointegration among the variables. Since six out of eleven results support to reject the null hypothesis at 1 %, 5 % or 10% significant levels, I am confident to conclude that there is cointegration among the five variables.

6.4 Long-run and short-run estimation.

Table 4 shows the long-run and short-run estimation of equation 2. Result from the estimation using Panel Dynamic Least Squares (DOLS) method is reported in column 2. 1% increase in per capita electricity consumption (EC) significantly increases per capita gross domestic product (GDP) by 0.85%. Every 1% increases in per capita renewable energy consumption and labor force participation significantly decreases GDP by 0.16 % and 0.03 % respectively. Also, for 1% increase in per capita stock significantly increases GDP by 1.28%.

Column 3 reports the estimation result using Panel Fully Modified Least Squares method (FMOLS). FMOLS method gives the same interpretation about the sign and the significance but magnitude. An increase in per capita electricity consumption (EC) by 1% significantly increases per capita gross domestic product (GDP) by 1.19% whereas 1% increases in per capita renewable energy consumption decreases it by 0.14%. Also, per capita gross domestic product (GDP) grows up by 0.94 % for every % increases in per capita renewable energy consumption. In addition, labor force participation significantly negatively affects per capita gross domestic product (GDP), with the ratio of 1:0.05.

Table 4 also reports the long-run and short-run estimation result using panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. The long-run results are similar in signs to DOLS and FMOLS methods. However, while per capita electricity consumption, renewable energy consumption and labor force participation significantly affects GDP at 5% significance level, per capita stock insignificantly influence GDP. The short-run estimation shows that electricity consumption, capital stock and labor force participation are positively related to GDP, that is, every percent increase in these variables will increase GDP by 1.31 %, 7.84% and 1.22 % respectively. Renewable energy still has negative impact on GDP, with 1% increase in renewable energy consumption decreases GDP by 4.45%.

Overall, the result suggests that electricity consumption along with capital stock signifi-

TABLE 3
Cointegration test result

Test		Statistic	Prob	Weighted Statistic	Prob
Alternative hypothesis: common AR coefs. (within-dimension)	Panel v-Statistic	-0.153	0.561	0.283	0.389
	Panel rho-Statistic	1.814	0.965	1.010	0.844
	Panel PP-Statistic	-1.408	0.079***	-2.902	0.002**
	Panel ADF-Statistic	-2.889	0.002**	-4.253	0.000*
Alternative hypothesis: individual AR coefs. (between-dimension)	Group rho-Statistic	3.192	0.9999		
	Group PP-Statistic	-2.496	0.006**		
	Group ADF-Statistic	-4.497	0.000*		
*; ** & *** indicate the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no cointegration among variables at 1% ,5% and 10% significance level respectively.					

cantly positively related to GDP.

TABLE 4
Equation (1) estimation result

Method		DOLS	FMOLS	ADRL
Long-run estimation	Ln_EC	0.851*	1.195*	2.574*
		0.132	0.105	0.112
	Ln_RE	-0.162*	-0.144*	-0.059*
		0.027	0.021	0.023
	Ln_CS	1.282*	0.945*	0.008*
		0.073	0.056	0.063
	LF	-0.033*	-0.051*	-0.021*
Short-run estimation		0.006	0.004	0.004
	COINTEQ01			-0.155
				0.02
	D(Ln_EC)			0.086
				0.065
	D(Ln_RE)			-0.069*
				0.016
	D(Ln_CS)			0.603*
				0.077
D(LF)			0.005	
			0.004	

6.5 State specific estimation.

Table 5 shows the long-run and short-run estimation result of equation 1 for individual state. Since I am mainly interested in how per capita electricity consumption affects per capita gross domestic product, I divide the states into two groups: Group Positive represents all the states with their estimations of equation 1 that has the coefficients of per capita electricity consumption is greater than zero. There are 21 states in this group reports that an increase in per capita electricity consumption significantly increases per capita gross product. Group Negative represents 10 states with their estimations

of equation 1 that has the coefficients of per capita electricity consumption is smaller than zero. Among these 10 states, there are only 2 states report the negative significance impact of electricity consumption on economic growth.

With regard to other inputs, 30 out of 50 states show a negative impact of renewable energy on economic growth. However, only 7 states shows that renewable energy significantly negatively affects state gross domestic product. In addition, most of the states show that capital stock positively drives economic growth. Furthermore, the sign of labor force participation varies. Labor force participation reduces economic growth in some states such as Arkansas, Delaware, Michigan, etc while it positively drives economy in other states such as California, Louisiana, Minnesota, etc.

6.6 Panel causality test.

Table 6 reports the panel causality test result using Pairwise Dumitrescu Hurlin Panel Causality Tests. The result shows that there is a unidirectional causality that runs from electricity consumption to economic growth, which confirms the relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth.

There are nine bidirectional causality between per capita gross domestic product and per capita stock; per capita renewable energy consumption and per capita gross domestic product; per capita renewable energy and per capita electricity consumption; capital stock and electricity consumption; labor force and electricity consumption; labor force and renew-

TABLE 5
State specific estimation result

Sign	State	Ln_EC	Ln_RE	Ln_CS	LF
Positive	<i>Alabama</i>	2.062 (0.663)*	-0.208(0.161)	0.676(1.080)	-0.014(0.011)
	<i>Alaska</i>	1.478(0.324)*	-0.242(0.095)**	-0.187(0.156)	-0.016(0.012)
	<i>Arizona</i>	5.231(7.379)	0.858(1.33)	1.672(1.464)	-0.0008(0.078)
	<i>Arkansas</i>	2.076(0.408)*	-0.123(0.356)	-0.335(0.450)	-0.055(0.022)**
	<i>California</i>	1.094(0.832)	-0.136(0.217)	2.116(0.216)	0.048(0.023)***
	<i>Colorado</i>	2.463(2.223)	0.257(0.254)	1.488(0.612)***	0.032(0.055)
	<i>Delaware</i>	2.609(1.655)	0.047(0.148)	0.622(1.058)	-0.065(0.026)***
	<i>Florida</i>	3.219(2.386)	0.403(0.525)	2.179(0.958)**	-0.036(0.077)
	<i>Georgia</i>	2.526(1.892)	0.226(0.667)	1.327(0.937)	-0.017(0.029)
	<i>Illinois</i>	2.897(0.882)*	0.019(0.144)	2.339(0.665)*	0.042(0.0034)
	<i>Iowa</i>	2.457(0.517)*	-0.187(0.045)*	0.604(0.547)	-0.039(0.010)*
	<i>Kansas</i>	2.631(0.510)*	-0.107(0.079)	1.147(0.755)	-0.042(0.033)
	<i>Louisiana</i>	5.025(2.411)***	-0.579(1.446)	0.301(2.113)	0.305(0.159)***
	<i>Maine</i>	2.902(1.283)**	-0.276(0.417)*	3.348(0.527)*	0.026(0.024)
	<i>Massachusetts</i>	0.029(1.292)	0.196(0.501)	2.355(0.354)*	0.119(0.083)
	<i>Michigan</i>	3.193(0.909)*	-0.164(0.363)	1.059(0.709)	-0.017(0.032)*
	<i>Minnesota</i>	0.239(0.632)	-0.284(0.153)***	2.949(0.429)*	0.042(0.021)***
	<i>Mississippi</i>	1.852(0.292)*	-0.247(0.081)*	0.353(0.299)	-0.004(0.006)
	<i>Missouri</i>	0.297(0.612)	-0.264(0.128)***	2.570(0.669)*	-0.002(0.026)
	<i>Montana</i>	12944.308(198289.3)	-388.925(59454.530)	33.225(4808.867)	-38.048(5829.017)
	<i>Nebraska</i>	3.921(0.928)*	0.184(0.212)	-1.426(0.789)***	-0.065(0.040)
	<i>Nevada</i>	1.437(3.515)	-0.146(0.243)	3.435(2.166)	-0.056(0.046)
	<i>New Hampshire</i>	1174.603(123325.8)	100.209(10588.000)	-50.896(5494.447)	4.678(497.059)
	<i>New Mexico</i>	4.528(1.436)*	-0.179(0.159)	-0.067(1.430)	-0.001(0.045)
	<i>New York</i>	2.054(0.649)*	0.145(0.163)	1.819(0.096)*	0.075(0.015)*
	<i>North Carolina</i>	6.893(3.823)***	0.278(0.953)	0.890(1.366)	-0.105(0.048)**
	<i>North Dakota</i>	1.568(0.368)*	0.025(0.151)	-0.175(0.298)	0.041(0.027)
	<i>Ohio</i>	3.128(1.595)***	-0.279(0.271)	2.883(0.353)*	-0.008(0.0058)
	<i>Oklahoma</i>	3.253(0.389)*	0.132(0.112)	0.447(0.489)	0.104(0.045)**
	<i>Oregon</i>	328.681(34989.29)	-125.615(18361.89)	-49.975(7667.439)	-9.721(1425.847)
	<i>Pennsylvania</i>	1.239(0.879)	-0.022(0.282)	0.956(0.374)**	0.139(0.078)***
	<i>Rhode Island</i>	5.116(3.056)	-0.118(0.202)	0.068(1.143)	-0.064(0.051)
	<i>South Carolina</i>	1.648(0.476)*	0.003(0.160)	1.740(0.575)*	-0.020(0.019)
<i>South Dakota</i>	2.439(1.515)	0.045(0.178)	-0.332(1.033)	0.064(0.029)**	
<i>Tennessee</i>	1.096(0.458)**	-0.062(0.149)	2.375(0.237)*	-0.012(0.011)	
<i>Texas</i>	5.328(3.685)	0.047(0.222)	1.296(1.616)	-0.058(0.079)	
<i>Utah</i>	4.937(2.056)**	0.166(0.207)	0.521(1.039)	0.040(0.043)	
<i>Vermont</i>	5.255(2.921)***	0.501(0.888)	0.590(1.377)	0.013(0.075)	
<i>West Virginia</i>	2.285(1.472)	-0.471(0.356)	0.624(1.336)	0.019(0.147)	
<i>Wisconsin</i>	2.047(0.857)**	-0.032(0.267)	0.994(0.708)	-0.002(0.023)	
Negative	<i>Connecticut</i>	-213.602 (14263.89)	-69.276(4579.672)	35.435(2279.861)	3.686(247.126)
	<i>Hawaii</i>	-2.601(4.217)	-0.688(0.727)	-3.198(3.624)	0.005(0.091)
	<i>Idaho</i>	-12.198(58.546)	10.517(55.260)	1.923(13.735)	0.530(2.459)
	<i>Indiana</i>	-0.808(0.889)	-0.875(0.200)*	4.105(0.797)*	-0.041(0.018)**
	<i>Kentucky</i>	-0.853(0.593)	-0.124(0.203)	3.218(0.444)*	0.071(0.047)
	<i>Maryland</i>	-0.770(2.159)	-0.423(0.624)	1.454(0.872)	0.068(0.161)
	<i>New Jersey</i>	-0.343(1.427)	-0.145(0.119)	2.171(0.496)*	0.037(0.041)
	<i>Verginia</i>	-0.366(0.704)	-0.011(0.118)	2.135(0.339)*	-0.042(0.010)*
	<i>Washington</i>	-0.975(0.501)***	-0.193(0.382)	2.078(0.443)*	0.088(0.022)*
	<i>Wyoming</i>	-1.585(0.459)*	0.206(0.052)*	1.964(0.165)*	-0.103(0.019)*

able energy; labor force and capital stock; labor force and GDP; and capital stock and renewable energy.

Overall, the result of panel causality test confirms the relationship between GDP and electricity consumption, as well as other input variables such as renewable energy, capital stock and labor force participation.

TABLE 6
Panel causality test result

Null hypothesis	W-Stat	Zbar-Stat	Prob
EC does not homogeneously cause GDP	3.410	-3.524	0.0004*
GDP does not homogeneously cause EC	6.819	1.116	0.265
RE does not homogeneously cause GDP	4.563	-1.955	0.051***
GDP does not homogeneously cause RE	12.449	8.777	0.000*
CS does not homogeneously cause GDP	2.250	-0.5103	0.000*
GDP does not homogeneously cause CS	7.809	2.462	0.013**
LF does not homogeneously cause GDP	7.564	2.129	0.033**
GDP does not homogeneously cause LF	5.221	8.664	0.000*
RE does not homogeneously cause EC	9.759	5.116	0.000*
EC does not homogeneously cause RE	9.917	5.329	0.000*
CS does not homogeneously cause EC	8.847	3.875	0.000*
EC does not homogeneously cause CS	9.259	4.434	0.000*
LF does not homogeneously cause EC	7.319	1.796	0.073***
EC does not homogeneously cause LF	8.848	3.875	0.000*
CS does not homogeneously cause RE	10.983	6.781	0.000*
RE does not homogeneously cause CS	7.726	2.348	0.019**
LF does not homogeneously cause RE	8.810	3.825	0.000*
RE does not homogeneously cause LF	9.587	4.882	0.000*
LF does not homogeneously cause CS	7.430	1.946	0.052***
CS does not homogeneously cause LF	11.485	7.467	0.000*

7 CONCLUSIONS

Despite the relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth has been

discussed widely in literature, there is limited evidence on the causal impact of the two variables at the state-level focus. This paper investigates the causal relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth by using panel data of fifty states in the U.S. over the period of 1990 to 2017. By controlling for renewable energy consumption, capital stock and labor force participation, I estimate the short-run and long-run elasticities of per capita gross domestic with respect to each input variable. The panel causality test is also conducted to report the causal relationship result.

The result shows that in the long-run, for every percent increase in per capita electricity consumption, per capita gross domestic product significantly increases by 0.85% (1.19%, 2.57%) by applying panel dynamic least squares (DOLS), panel fully modified least squares method (FMOLS), and panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model respectively. In the short-run, 1% increase in electricity consumption increases economic growth by 1.31%. The causality test also suggests that there is a causality that runs from electricity consumption to GDP. In addition, it also reports nine bidirectional causality among variables, which implies the importance of other inputs in the development of economy. Furthermore, the long-run estimation result shows the negative relationship between renewable energy consumption and economic growth. This result has an important implication for the U.S. energy policies because the U.S. aims to switch to 100% renewable energy sources. This transformation possibly negatively affects economic growth in the long run.

Moreover, the different result of specific state estimation analyzes the importance of understanding the impact of electricity consumption on economic growth of each state, which potentially provide recommendation for policy makers before making energy efficiency policy. For instance, on one hand, in the states that there is a positive relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth such as Illinois and Tennessee, policy makers should draw attention to the payoffs of energy efficiency policy in the long run. On the

other hand, electricity consumption negatively affects economic growth in some states such as Washington or Wyoming, energy efficiency incentive program should be widely adopted. Similarly, the specific state estimation result reports the relationship between renewable energy consumption and economic growth. Therefore, it provides recommendation of paying more attention to either policy makers should promote renewable energy consumption to promote the economy.

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